

Gamow Factor Derivation Applied to n_1 - n_2 (index of refraction) Reflection-Refraction

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 20, 2026

In (1), an outline of the derivation of the Gamow factor for alpha decay from a nucleus is given. In one dimension, the approach considers three regions in space, one with an incident and reflected free particle wavefunction, the second (within a square V barrier) with an exponentially growing and falling solution, and the third, with a single free particle wavefunction $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx+\text{phase})$ representing the escaped alpha particle. Alpha decay is treated as a quantum tunneling problem and the wavefunction and its first derivative d/dx must be continuous.

A second step in (1), however, is to assume that one may write a time related wavefunction as $\exp(-g t)$, where $d/dt \text{ partial Integral } dx \text{ (region) } W^*W = \frac{1}{2} (-i W^* d/dx W + i W d/dx W^*)$. This may appear to be a quantum mechanical equation, but we argue that this is nothing more than the classical continuity equation. In fact, in (2) we argued that quantum mechanics does not exist without classical equations. In particular, the quantum free particle wavefunctions $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ follow $\exp(iEt)\exp(-iEt) = 1$ and $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ to link them classical densities in time and space for particles moving with a constant speed. If there is a decay in time and space, then the appropriate classical equation is the continuity one. Writing $d/dt \text{ partial } d(t) = \text{constant } d(t)$ yields the familiar $\exp(-g t)$ form.

We apply the ideas of the Gamow factor to a set of photons bouncing back and forth in an n_1 1-dimensional cavity surrounded by n_2 ($n_2 > n_1$) index of refraction material. In this case, if the photons are synchronized then one may follow them classically. The catch is that the probability to reflect or refract is quantum. In general, one would not write $\exp(-g t)$ in such a scenario, but would formally write an equation of the form: fraction of remaining photons = $R^{\text{Integer}(t/t_1)}$, where R is the probability to reflect and $\text{Integer}(t/t_1)$ is the number of cycles. If, however, the probability to refract is very small, we show that one may in fact obtain the same result as in the case of $\exp(-g t)$ for $g \ll 1$. Alternatively, if the cavity is small in length and the speed of the particle (c in the case of light) is large, one could approximate the situation by $d/dt \text{ partial } d(t) = \text{constant } d(t)$ and then obtain $\exp(-g t)$, having the photons no longer in deterministic motion.

Gamow Factor and Alpha Decay

The consideration of an alpha particle existing in a nucleus and trying to tunnel out was presented by Gamow many years ago. One may use a standard continuity of wavefunction and its d/dx derivative in the 1-dimensional case and consider three regions. The first is one of an incoming free particle which reflects or partially enters a square barrier of height V and length l . The sum of an exponentially growing and falling wavefunction are used in this region. Finally, one has the free alpha particle moving in one direction in the third region. In (1), the three wavefunctions are given by:

Region 3: $A \exp(ikx + i \text{ phase}_1) \exp(-iEt)$ ((1a))

Region 2: $B_1 \exp(k_1 x) + B_2 \exp(-k_1 x)$ ((1b))

Region 1: $C_1 \exp(ikx + i \text{ phase } 2) \exp(-iEt) + C_2 \exp(-kx + i \text{ phase } 3) \exp(-iEt)$ ((1c))

In (1), the results for continuity using some approximations are provided and we simply state them here.

$k/k' \text{ approx} = \sqrt{E/(V-E)}$ ((2a)) $B_1 \text{ approx} = B_2 \text{ approx} = A$ ((2b))

$C_1 \text{ approx} = C_2 \text{ approx} = .5A (k'/k) \exp(k'l)$ ((2c))

A key feature which we wish to focus on is what is called the conservation of probability in (1):

$d/dt \text{ partial } \int dx \text{ range } W^* W = 2 (1/2) \hbar/m \{ -i W^* d/dx W + i W d/dx W^* \}$ ((3))

On the RHS, the first factor of 2 represents the fact that an alpha particle may emerge from the right or left (i.e. there are really two V barriers in the problem, although only one has been discussed above due to symmetry). The factor $1/2$ is the averaging factor for the average momentum in $\{ \}$. In (1), it is assumed that $W(x,t)$ goes as $\exp(-g t)$ for the time portion.

We stress that ((3)) is nothing more than the classical continuity equation:

$d/dt \text{ partial density}(x,t) + \text{grad dot } (v \text{ density}) = 0$ ((4))

In other words, we argue that there is nothing particularly quantum about the calculation ((3)) in this particular example. It was already found that one has ((2b)) from quantum mechanics. C is the incident amplitude and A is the amplitude of interest, that of the alpha particle. Amplitudes are converted into probabilities through W^*W . We argue that in the free particle case this is directly tied to the link between classical and quantum physics. In other words, the two are not separate, but complementary as argued in (2). In particular, $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ must be consistent with the classical uniform probability in time and space, i.e..

$P(t) = \text{constant}_1 \rightarrow \exp(iEt)\exp(-iEt)$ and $P(x) = \text{constant}_2 \rightarrow \exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ ((5))

Thus, if an alpha particle escapes, then one should ensure that the continuity equation holds because this is a classical equation which is linked to the quantum mechanical result ((3)). Furthermore, we note that $\exp(-g t)$ is a continuous approximation to a discrete event situation. We discuss this further in the section on n_1 - n_2 reflection-refraction. We argue that even though quantum mechanical features are critical, problems also use classical features at the same time. In other words, we argue that there is nothing particularly quantum mechanical about $\exp(-g t)$ in the way it is used in this problem. In (1), the result of ((3)) is given by:

$g \text{ approx} = 4 \sqrt{E/2m} (1/(q+l)) k/k' \exp(-2k'l)$ ((6))

One may note that in the solution of ((6)), (1) uses $2 \hbar v / m \lambda$ for the RHS of ((3)). The 2 arises from the two sides for alpha escape, $\hbar v / m \lambda$ is the speed and λ is the flux of the alpha particle. This is equated to the d/dt partial Integral dx density(x,t) in ((3)).

In other words, one has the classical situation of:

$$d/dt \text{ partial } d(t) = \text{constant } d(t) \quad ((7))$$

which yields a falling density $\exp(-2 \lambda t)$. One does not require quantum mechanics for this or for $2 \lambda \lambda$, calling λ flux. This is a classical statement. Connecting λ to E and V , however, is quantum mechanics.

We now try to apply the above ideas to the case of a set of photons trapped in an n_1 1-dimensional cavity in n_2 (index of refraction). It seems that classical and $\exp(-\lambda t)$ notions appear more clearly in this situation.

n_1 - n_2 Reflection-Refraction

Consider a set of photons moving together as a group with speed c in an $n_1=1$ 1-dimensional cavity surrounded by material with $n_2 > n_1$. At each end, the photons may reflect or refract, and this probability R, F is given by the quantum mechanical result from (3):

$$\text{Flux to reflect} = (c_2 - c) / (c_2 + c) * (c_2 - c) / (c_2 + c) \quad \text{where } c_2 = nc \quad ((8a))$$

$$\text{Flux to refract} = (2c_2 / (c_1 + c_2)) * (2c_2 / (c_1 + c_2)) \quad ((8b))$$

Probability is given by Flux/ c for a reflected photon and Flux/ c_2 for a refracted. A refracted photon means an escaped or lost photon, just like an escaped alpha particle.

We argue that this problem is very similar in nature to the alpha decay one, even though one has quantum refraction and not a V barrier. We argue that one may clearly see classical equations at work if one considers the length of the $n_1=1$ cavity to be very large. In such a case, it takes:

$$T_1 = l/c \quad ((9))$$

time to traverse the cavity and then reflect or refract. As a result, one sees immediately that a $\exp(-\lambda t)$ factor does not describe this problem in general. We, however, consider the case of a F , the probability to reflect being very small. R is the probability to reflect) Then

$$\text{fraction of photons}(t) \text{ approx} = R^{\text{Integer}(t/T_1)} \quad ((10))$$

Here Integer(t) means to take the integer value and drop any fraction.

((10)) becomes:

Fraction of photons left = $(1-R \text{ power } (t/t_1)) = 1 - (1-F) \text{ power } t/t_1 \approx F \text{ Integer } \{ t/t_1 \}$ ((11))

((11)) is of the same form as $\exp(-2g t)$ which represents the fraction of alpha particles still in the nucleus. Then:

Fraction of escaped alpha particles = $1 - \exp(-2g t) \approx 2g t$. ((12))

G was proportional to the flux of the escaped alpha particle multiplied by 2 and then by speed. Here 2 is not needed because we have deterministic photon motion.

Here $F = \text{flux of the escaped photon} / c$. ((12))

One may see that both ((11)) and ((12)) are proportional to t and a factor linked with flux to escape. The exact values of the fluxes are quantum mechanical and are different as the alpha particle and n_1 - n_2 reflection-refraction problem are not the same, but the strategies are the same. Both use wavefunctions, their continuity (and that of the d/dx derivative) and then the continuity equation, which is classical. Above, we do not directly use the continuity equation because we have a discrete picture. If one had photons moving in both directions and spread out over the length l of the $n_1=1$ cavity, then one would apply the classical continuity equation ((4)) (and the factor of 2 would be linked to flux because photons would be refracting from both sides at the same time) even though the probability to refract (which is considered small) is calculated using quantum mechanics.

In principle, we argue that the formalism of the alpha decay through tunnelling of an alpha particle which exists in the nucleus and is treated in a statistical manner is identical to the loss of refracted photons from a set of photons moving statistically (not deterministically) in a 1-dimensional cavity. In such a case, one uses:

$d/dt \text{ partial } d(t) = d(t) * \text{constant}$ and obtains an $\exp(-2 g t)$ type of solution.

One may note that F , the probability to refract is linked to $(C/A) = 2c_2/(c_1+c_2)$, i.e. this term is squared and divided by c^2 . AA is the incident flux at a given time and so the escaped flux is linked to AA , the incident and one may write $d(t)$ in the above equation (RHS).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the tunnelling of an already existing alpha particle in a nucleus, considered by Gamow, shows how quantum mechanics and classical mechanics work together. To solve for the amplitude of the escaped alpha particle, one must use quantum mechanics, i.e. a wavefunction and its continuity in x (and continuity of d/dx wavefunction). After that, however, the flux of escaped alpha particle $\propto AA$ (from $A \exp(ikx)$) is a classical type form. $AA = \text{flux}$ because $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$. In other words, $\exp(ipx)$ is a quantum expression, but is tied to a classical one through $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$. Thus, quantum and classical mechanics are not

independent. Furthermore, a conservation of probability equation used to find $\exp(-2gt)$ as the probability of an alpha particle not escaping is identical to the classical continuity equation.

We apply these ideas to the 1-dimensional situation of photons in a cavity with $n_1=1$, surrounded by $n_2>n_1$ material. Photons are lost through refraction and so this problem should be very similar to the alpha particle escape one. We note that if the photons move in a bunch, then the motion is deterministic and one would use $1-R$ power t/t_1 , where t_1 is the time to traverse the cavity and R the probability to reflect, to find the fraction of remaining photons. This is not $\exp(-2gt)$. If, however, R is almost 1, then we show that the result is of the form of $\exp(-2gt)$ for g tiny. We then argue that it is only in the statistical situation in which one has photons throughout the cavity and moving in both directions that one would apply the classical continuity equation. The flux of refracting photons is proportional to the flux of photons within the cavity and so we argue that in such a case one has: $d/dt \text{ partial } d(t) = \text{constant } d(t)$ and one may obtain an $\exp(-\text{constant } t)$ solution. Thus, we argue that there is nothing particularly quantum mechanical about the $\exp(-gt)$ factor for a wavefunction because it becomes $\exp(-2gt)$ for the classical probability and has the same physical form.

References

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